

Impact of Combined Sensory and Auditory Distraction Using Eye Massager and Colored Noise on Pediatric Dental Anxiety During Extractions

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Abstract

Background - Innovative non-pharmacological anxiety management systems in pediatric dentistry enhance the comfort and cooperation of young patients during dental procedures. These advancements focus on optimising distraction methods for better efficacy and reduced physiological stress.

Aim - To compare and evaluate the impact of combined sensory and auditory distraction using an eye massager and colored noise on pediatric dental anxiety during extractions.

Methods - An in vivo study was conducted to evaluate the efficacy and efficiency of different distraction methods. Forty children aged 8-12 years, with Frankl Behaviour rating scale scores of 2 and 3, who required primary tooth extractions, were selected and equally divided into 4 groups (n=10 per group). Group A served as the Control group, Group B received Eye Massager, Group C received the Eye Massager with Pink Noise, and Group D received the Eye Massager with White Noise. Anxiety levels were assessed using Venham's Picture Test, Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and pulse oximetry before and after local anaesthesia administration.

Results - The combination of eye massager with pink noise achieved significant anxiety reduction and higher patient relaxation compared to other groups. The eye massager with pink noise group demonstrated superior efficacy in lowering pulse rates and anxiety scores in pediatric dental patients.

Conclusion - The study demonstrated that the combination of an eye massager with pink noise is an effective and non-invasive method that could be a practical tool for anxiety management in clinical settings, providing a convenient alternative to traditional methods.

Keywords - Pediatric dental anxiety, Eye massager, Pink noise, White noise, Audio analgesia

Introduction

Dental anxiety remains a persistent challenge in paediatric dentistry often presenting as fear avoidance and uncooperative behaviour during invasive procedures such as local anaesthesia administration and extractions.¹ These reactions can prolong chairside time complicate behaviour guidance, and negatively shape a child's future attitude toward dental care.² Traditionally, behaviour management has relied on pharmacological means or basic communicative guidance; however, pharmacological agents carry risks of adverse effects, while basic techniques may be insufficient for highly anxious children.³

In response, dentistry has increasingly adopted non pharmacological approaches that reduce anxiety while maintaining safety and acceptability for children.⁴ Audio analgesia relief of pain or distress through auditory stimulation such as music or noise has been used for decades and is considered a valuable adjunct for anxiety and pain

modulation during dental treatment.⁵ More recently, "coloured noise" (such as white and pink noise) has gained interest because it can mask unpleasant operatory sounds and create a steady auditory environment that promotes calmness.³

Alongside auditory strategies, sensory-based relaxation devices are being explored to provide an additional calming pathway.⁶ Eye massagers may help reduce anxiety by delivering gentle pressure around the periocular region, encouraging relaxation and dampening stress responses, making them an appealing, non-invasive distraction tool in children. Combining sensory relaxation (eye massager) with auditory masking (pink or white noise) may therefore provide a multimodal distraction that is more effective

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than either approach alone during anxietyprovoking procedures such as extractions.³ Despite the individual efficacy of these methods, limited literature exists comparing the specific effects of different colored noise frequencies when combined with tactile distraction in a clinical setting⁷

The present invivo study was designed to compare the effect of an eye massager alone and an eye massager combined with pink noise or white noise on paediatric dental anxiety during extractions. By utilising subjective and objective measures, including VAS, Venham's tests, and pulse rate changes, this study aims to identify the most effective non-invasive protocol for enhancing comfort and compliance in pediatric dentistry.⁸

Materials & Method

An in-vivo, comparative study was conducted in the Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry to compare and evaluate the efficacy of combined sensory and auditory distraction. The study was approved by the institutional ethical committee, and informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants.

A total of 40 children, aged between 8 and 12 years, who required primary tooth extractions, were selected for the study. Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria such as Children aged 8-12 years who had a Frankl Behaviour Rating Scale score of 2 or 3, with primary teeth indicated for extraction, and who were willing to participate in the study were included.

Group A: Control group (No intervention).

- Group B: Received Eye Massager distraction.
- Group C: Received Eye Massager with Pink Noise.

Group D: Received Eye Massager with White Noise.

Fig 1: Visual analogue scale (VAS)

Fig 2: Venham's Picture Test (VPT)

Anxiety, pulse rate and pain assessment

Three parameters were used to evaluate the child's response: anxiety, pulse rate and pain were assessed using three standard measures. Pulse rate was recorded with a finger pulse oximeter before and after local anaesthesia. Anxiety was measured using Venham's Picture/Behaviour Test (Fig-2) at the same two time

points, and pain was evaluated using a childfriendly Visual Analogue Scale (Fig-1) before and after local anaesthesia.

Intervention protocol

For groups 2, 3 and 4, the assigned anxietymanagement technique was initiated shortly before local anaesthesia and maintained throughout the injection. In Group 2, only an eye massager was applied around the eyes to provide gentle periorbital pressure, block visual triggers, and offer rhythmic tactile stimulation that helps relax and distract the child. In Group 3, the eye massager was combined with pink noise delivered through earphones at a comfortable, preset volume, while in Group 4 the eye massager was combined with white noise in the same manner. Group 1 received no distraction device or sound and only routine communication. In all four groups, local anaesthesia was administered using standard technique and ageappropriate dosage

Outcome recording

For each child, the following were recorded:

- Preintervention pulse rate, VPT/BPT anxiety score, and VAS pain score.
- Postintervention pulse rate, VPT/BPT anxiety score, and VAS pain score after completion of local anaesthesia.

Fig 3- Administration of local anesthesia without using any intervention (control group) & Administration of local anesthesia by using eye massager

Fig 4- Administration of local anesthesia by using eye massager and pink noise

Fig 5- Administration of local anesthesia by using eye massager and white noise

Results

The collected data were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics and post hoc analysis were applied

to determine the significance of differences among the groups. The analysis revealed a reduction in anxiety levels across all intervention groups compared to the control group. Among the experimental groups, the greatest reduction in pulse rate was observed in Group C (Eye Massager with Pink Noise), followed by Group D and Group B.

- Pulse Rate: Significant changes were noted. For example, Group C showed a substantial decrease in pulse rate post-intervention compared to pre-intervention values, indicating a strong calming effect. (Graph-1)
- Venham Scores: Both Venham Picture Test and Behaviour scores improved significantly in the intervention groups, with the pink noise combination proving most effective. (Graph-2)
- VAS Anxiety Scores: Intergroup comparisons demonstrated significant differences in anxiety reduction, with Group C showing the lowest anxiety scores post-treatment. (Graph-3)

Graph 1: Comparison of change in pulse rate within each group

Graph 2: Comparison of the change in Venham's picture test within each group

Graph 3: Comparison of change visual analogue scale within each group

Discussion

Managing dental anxiety in pediatric patients presents unique challenges, particularly during injections and extractions, where fear and avoidance behaviours are common.⁹ Non-

pharmacological distraction methods are increasingly preferred because they are simple to deliver chairside and generally well accepted by children. In the present study, a combined sensory (eye massager) and auditory (coloured noise) approach was evaluated to reduce anxiety during extraction procedures.

Audio analgesia relief of pain or distress through auditory stimulation has been described for decades in dentistry and is considered a useful adjunct for anxiety control, it showed that audio distraction effectively alleviates anxiety in pediatric dental patients by diverting attention from stressful stimuli.¹⁰ Recent paediatric dentistry approaches have expanded this concept to include "coloured noise" such as pink noise and white noise. Abed et al. (2025)³ and Kolhe et al. (2024) suggest that such auditory environments can shift the autonomic nervous system response, reducing physiological stress.¹¹

Pink noise is described as having more energy at lower frequencies with a softer, more balanced sound that can better mask environmental operatory noises, producing a calming effect. Kolhe et al. (2024)¹¹ found that pink noise was superior to white noise in maintaining stable pulse rates during dental procedures. White noise contains all frequencies across the audible spectrum equally and is described as working at the midbrain level with an added benefit of strengthening focus, although some studies suggest it may be less soothing than pink noise for relaxation (Kunusoth et al., 2022).¹²

Alongside auditory masking, sensory relaxation devices such as eye massagers may reduce anxiety by applying gentle pressure around the peri-orbital region. Kunusoth et al. (2022)¹² found that an eye massage device combined with natural sounds significantly reduced pulse rates and fear scores during inferior alveolar nerve blocks. The mechanism is believed to involve stimulating acupressure points (such as the Yin Tang point), which promotes parasympathetic activation and lowers stress hormones like cortisol (Moyer et al 2004).¹³

The rationale for combining an eye massager with coloured noise is that multi-sensory distraction may provide a stronger attentional "pull" than either modality alone. Abed et al. (2025)³ specifically supported this synergy, reporting that the combination of eye massage and sound provided the best relaxation effect compared to single interventions. This aligns with the "gate control theory" of pain, where multiple non-painful sensory inputs (touch and sound) can close the gate to painful stimuli (Singh et al 2014).⁹

In the present study, all intervention groups showed improvement compared with the control group across measures such as pulse rate and anxiety scales, with the eye massager with pink noise group showing the greatest reduction. These findings align with Kolhe et al. (2024)¹¹, who emphasised the efficacy of pink noise, and Gala et al. (2024),¹⁴ who confirmed the benefits of sensory eye distraction. The comparatively better performance of pink noise in this setting may be explained by its softer frequency profile, which creates a less intrusive and more soothing auditory floor compared to the "hiss" of white noise (Abed et al 2025).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of a combined sensory and auditory distraction system specifically an eye massager paired with colored noise presents a promising non-pharmacological alternative to traditional anxiety management in pediatric care. Its non-invasive nature, combined with the synergistic benefits of tactile relaxation and auditory masking, positions it as a viable option for reducing dental anxiety during extractions. The eye

massager with pink noise demonstrated superior efficacy in lowering pulse rates and anxiety scores compared to single-modality or control interventions, potentially leading to smoother procedures and better patient compliance. Hence, this combined approach is recommended as an innovative, effective, and child-friendly behaviour management system in pediatric dentistry.

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